

Requirements for Design of Cultural - Entertainment Center Building

S. A. Qodirova¹, R. I. Allimdjanov², L. Sh. Raximov³, R. X. Qurbonov⁴

¹Associate Professor Tashkent Institute of Architecture and Civil Engineering, Uzbekistan

²Senior Teacher Tashkent Institute of Architecture and Civil Engineering, Uzbekistan

^{3,4}Assistant Tashkent Institute of Architecture and Civil Engineering, Uzbekistan

ABSTRACT: The buildings of the cultural centers are designed to carry out large-scale cultural activities among the population. At the same time, it plays a dominant role as the main building in rural and urban population centers, as it unites and brings together all segments of the population.

KEYWORDS: public entertainment part, clubs, stage, administrative-economic, audience, dance hall.

INTRODUCTION

Since independence, political and spiritual stability in the Republic of Uzbekistan, reforms to democratize society, social and scientific-technical progress have developed the creative works in the field of rural architecture and construction in the regions of the country. The work on architectural design and the use of new methods of construction using new building materials, which are more functionally perfect, has been expanded. In particular, the development of rural and urban architecture of the Republic, changes in the cultural and educational spheres of the people, along with modern housing, requires the expansion of cultural centers, public buildings - cultural and educational centers and sports facilities. One of the main problems today is the increase in the number of institutions – cultural and entertainment buildings to hold meetings for people to spend their leisure time delightfully. Therefore, the cultural and educational building intended for the project is one of the architecturally perfect public buildings of cultural institutions in these areas, adapted for construction in villages and cities.

Table 1.

Types of cultural and entertainment centers	Construction site	Spectator capacity (seats)	The ratio of number of the audience to the capacity cultural center
1. Rural Cultural Center	In the rural production area, in the residential area	150-400	1:02-1:0,25
2. Rural Culture House	In the center of the residential area	300-700	1:03-1:04
3. District House of Culture	The administrative center of the district, in the residential area	500-800	1:0,7-1:0,8
4. Buildings of the City Cultural and entertainment Centers	It unites the district center of the city	300-700	1:0,6- 1:0,7
5. City House of Culture	The public center of the city	500-1000	1:0,9- 1:1

Currently, the most notable types of cultural and entertainment centers are mainly divided into two parts, one - the public entertainment part and the second part is intended for conducting clubs. In addition, there are special types of cultural and educational centers, such as youth centers, children's, chess, aero club, cultural and educational centers for writers.

Requirements for Design of Cultural - Entertainment Center Building

THE MAIN FINDINGS AND RESULTS

Cultural and entertainment centers are usually designed on the basis of a special assignment, the capacity of the entertainment part, the cultural and educational center is based on the norms of the CRN (Construction Regulation Norms). Depending on the rural conditions, other types of rooms can be included in the cultural and entertainment center.

All types of cultural and entertainment centers are divided into three main groups depending on their function: spectator rooms; cultural and educational center rooms; service and administrative rooms.

The rooms of the building of the cultural and educational center are divided into 3 groups:

- A** - Spectator section rooms;
- B** - Rooms of the cultural and entertainment center;
- C** - Auxiliary and administrative rooms.

A. The spectator section is designed to conduct a variety of public, spiritual, educational activities and recreation in the building of the cultural and entertainment center. It consists of three groups - spectator group, demonstration group and complexes:

- A complex of spectators with a viewing hall, foyer and dining room with a lobby, storage of equipment, a service room;
- The complex of the demonstration group - includes a house area, a service room, a cinema room;
- The stage was selected on the basis of the CRN (Construction Regulation Norms), depending on the type of cultural and entertainment center.

In Type 1 and Type 2 cultural and educational centers, the lobby is both for the cultural and entertainment center part and for the spectator part.

B. The rooms of the cultural and entertainment center are divided into three groups:

- Club and lecture room;
- Lounges;
- Rooms serving as library.
- Rooms in the group of lectures and clubs - hall and auditorium, 2-3 rooms for clubs, etc.
- The lounge consisting of a dance hall, a room for playing table tennis, a billiard table, a dining room - a buffet.
- The library for rural and urban residents consists of a reading room, a book storage room and a staff room.

C. Employees' and administrative and utility rooms: - lobby, wardrobe, toilets, administration rooms, methodical and warehouse utility rooms.

Rural cultural and educational centers have the same possibility to integrate with other institutions as they do with other buildings.

For example: - cinema, gym, museum or exhibition halls, etc. with the mahalla guzar (neighborhood complex) of the cultural and educational center. In this case, the work program of the institution will be rich and colorful in all respects. However, it should be borne in mind that the institutions should be well connected to each other, and each should be able to serve both together and separately.

In recent years, in the field of construction of cultural and entertainment centers, there is a desire for activities that are unique to the activities of the cultural and educational center (amateur art, association of common interests, spending time with entertainment).

Due to the lack of spectator sports facilities, libraries and other recreational facilities in the vicinity, the universal functions of clubs have been preserved in many rural areas.

There is a need to create special club buildings in the city, specializing in creative activities (folk art houses, amateur clubs), communication on interests (collectors in various fields, car enthusiasts, retirees' clubs, youth homes, etc.) and similar activities.

One of the most notable types of cultural and entertainment centers today are the cultural and educational center, which consists of two parts, one - the public entertainment (spectator) part and the other - the club section.

It would be expedient to build a network of cultural and entertainment institutions to the extent that they cover the production areas and the population of the district. Since the building of the cultural and educational center is a compositional element as a community center of the village, it should be an integrated cultural center, combined with separate or joint buildings on the land allotted for its function.

The site of the cultural and entertainment center will be constructed in the public center of the city or in the green zone of the residential area with a total area of not more than 0.5 m at least 12m away from the streets located on the red line. The following will be located on the site: Cultural and entertainment center complex; car accommodation for guests with 20 - 25 s / c

Requirements for Design of Cultural - Entertainment Center Building

(20 - 25 seats / car); A ring road with a width of not less than 3.0 m around the cultural center; water capacity (basin) for fire safety with $d = 6\text{m}$, depth $h = 2.4\text{m}$ - fountain; a recreation area with chairs - an indoor courtyard, which will be built in addition to the atrium-type Cultural and Educational Center complex; a farm yard with a production workshop and a garage with 4 j / m (including two buses); the remaining area is entered by green zones and added to the water flow path. In front of the building it is necessary to create a ceremonial public area with fountains, flower beds, waiting areas and rest areas with long benches. It is also required to provide temporary accommodation for cars and buses for 5 - 10 s / c (in the transverse profile of the road zone strip belonging to the side of the city streets). [2]

Rooms for recreation and entertainment in the building of the Cultural and Educational Center, rooms for clubs and studios, rooms for information purposes are accepted per student on the calculation area, including:

- Table for 1 person - 3 m², with a computer - 4-6 m²;
- 1 person, in the class of sculptor, music and choreography, aerobics - 5-6 m², for some types of classes - 7-8 m²;
- Studios 9-12 m² for classes, 12-15 m² for classes with a teacher, at least 18 m² for classes on two pianos.
- Guest and circle rooms for 10-15 people must be at least 30 m², orchestra, dance, choreography classrooms 50-60 m² and more.

The height of choreography, aerobics, shaping, dance halls must be at least 4.2 m, the height of acrobatics and circus training halls - 6-8 m. The halls should have dressing rooms with rest rooms.

Painting, ganch carving, sculpture, ceramics rooms must be equipped with appropriate technology. Administration and service rooms are provided at the rate of 6 m² for per employee. The auditoriums of the building of the cultural and educational center shall be designed taking into account paragraph/section 3.109. Hall, stage or stage dimensions must be provided in the project assignment. Pop halls with 100 seats must have an area of at least 27 m², in halls with 150-200 seats must have an area of at least 36 m². There will be a presidium and artists' rooms (from 15 m²) in front of the pop halls. In the foyer and dance halls, in small auditoriums, the pop hall area should be at least 12 m² (4x3 m). Audience rooms of cultural and educational centers, concert and theater halls should be designed taking into account the requirements of spectator institution's needs and requirements.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, it should be noted that today the demand for cultural and entertainment center buildings is growing among the population. Therefore, in the design of the building of the cultural and entertainment center, it is necessary to develop a project of the building, which will serve the population for many years, in accordance with the norms and rules of urban planning.

REFERENCES

- 1) Ubaydullaev X.M., Khidoyatov T.A., Abdurahmanov Y.I., Korobovtsev G.I., Mansurov Ya.M. Architectural Design: A Study Guide. - T.: 2012.
- 2) Ubaydullaev HM, Inogamova MM, Typological bases of design of residential and public buildings (textbook) T. "Heir" 2009.
- 3) Gelfond A.L. Arkhitekturnoe proektirovanie obshchestvennyx zdaniy i sooruzheniy: Uchebnoe posobie. - M.: Architecture-S, 2010,
- 4) SHNK 2.08.02-09 "Public buildings and structures"
- 5) www.archrecord.construction.com